

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

From which country are you completing this survey?	country_list
What is your gender?	Female Male Non-binary / Other Prefer not to say
Which age group do you belong to?	Under 25 25-34 35-44 45-54 55+ Prefer not to say
What is your highest level of education completed?	High school diploma or equivalent BA / BSc (Bachelor's degree) MA / MSc (Master's degree) PhD or equivalent (Doctoral level) Other (please specify): _____ I prefer not to answer
What is your field of education? <i>We refer here to your academic background.</i>	Conservation/ Restoration Heritage science (chemistry, physics, biology applied to heritage) Archaeology Architecture and Building Engineering Museum studies or cultural heritage management Digital technologies / Informatics Education or communication History / Art history I prefer not to answer
Which type of organization do you work for?	Museum Archive Library Cultural heritage association or NGO University / Higher education institution Research institute / Laboratory Public administration (e.g., cultural heritage authority, governmental agency) Private company (e.g., consultancy, technology provider) Self-employed / Independent expert
What's your level of experience in your current professional role?	Less than 1 year 1-3 years 4-8 years 8+ years

What role do you mainly hold in your organization? Please select the option that best describes your actual function in the field of cultural heritage, regardless of your institutional title (e.g., researcher, professor, consultant)	Conservation and Collection Care (e.g. Conservator/Restorer, Heritage Scientist, Curator, Architect, Built Heritage Engineer) Research and Education (e.g. Historian, Archaeologist, Museum Educator, Cultural Heritage Theorist) Technical and Digital Innovation (e.g. Digitization Expert, Digital Collection Manager, VR/AR Specialist, Data Engineer) Administration and Management (e.g. Director, Project Manager, Policy Officer, Institutional Coordinator)
Can you be more specific?	Conservator/Restorer Heritage scientist Curator / Archivist Architect / Built heritage specialist
Can you be more specific?	Historians and archaeologists Museum educators / heritage interpreters
Can you be more specific?	Digitization experts (3D scanning, digital archiving) Database and digital collection managers VR-AR specialist

CONSERVATOR/RESTORER

Which digital tools or technologies do you currently use in your conservation and restoration work?	High-resolution digital photography
	Multispectral imaging (UV, IR, X-ray, etc.)
	3D modelling
	Software for restoration documentation
	Spectroscopic tools (XRF, Raman, FTIR, etc.)
	Radiography and tomography (X-ray, CT scan)
	Infrared thermography
	Digital microscopy
	I don't use digital tools
	Other (please specify) _____
What types of data do you currently use for heritage conservation?	Photographic or high-resolution images
	3D scans
	Environmental monitoring data (temperature, humidity, pollutants, etc.)
	Chemical or physical analyses
	Historical documentation
	Structural monitoring data
	Advanced scientific imaging data (radiography, thermography, multispectral)
	Stratigraphic data (paint stratigraphy, material layers)
	Spectroscopic data (FTIR, Raman, XRF, etc.)
	Audio and video materials
Other (please specify) _____	

Are the data you work with collected in real time?	Yes, continuously collected and updated (e.g., environmental sensors) Yes, but only in specific situations or at scheduled intervals No, data collection occurs manually or only as needed I'm not sure / Not applicable Other (please specify): _____
Which digital tools or technologies do you use to assess and monitor the condition of cultural heritage objects, sites, or environments?	Environmental sensors (e.g., humidity, temperature, pollutants) Multispectral or hyperspectral imaging systems Crack monitors or structural monitoring devices Continuous condition monitoring systems Data loggers or automated recording devices I do not use digital tools for monitoring Other (please specify): _____
What are the main challenges in monitoring heritage conservation conditions?	Difficulty obtaining accurate and reliable data Lack of adequate technological tools High cost of tools, systems, or software Complexity in interpreting data Difficulty in maintaining digital tools Integration difficulties between traditional and digital practices I don't experience particular difficulties Other (please specify) _____
Are your data digitally structured and accessible?	Yes, in a structured and searchable digital system (e.g., database, archive, platform) Yes, but scattered across different systems or not fully interoperable Partially, some data are digitized but not searchable No, most data are unstructured or in physical format Other (please specify): _____
In what format are your data available?	Unstructured files (PDF, Word, etc.) Relational databases Scientific image formats (TIFF, RAW, DICOM, etc.) 3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, glTF, point clouds) Proprietary software formats Tabular datasets (CSV, Excel, etc.) Other (please specify): _____
Do you use any standards or protocols for data management and interoperability?	Dublin Core LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects) CIDOC CRM (Conceptual Reference Model) EODEM (Exchange of Data for Heritage Science) IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) OGC standards (e.g., GeoJSON, WMS, WFS) DOI (Digital Object Identifier) or ARK (Archival Resource Key) I don't use specific standards or protocols Other (please specify): _____

Do you use collaborative digital platforms to facilitate the sharing and collaborative management of restoration data?	Yes, platforms internal to my institution Yes, external or open-source platforms (e.g., Trello, Jira, GitHub, Slack) No, but I'd be interested in using them No, I don't see their usefulness Other (please specify) _____
What are the main difficulties in sharing conservation-related data?	Compatibility issues between different software and file formats Legal or institutional restrictions on data sharing Lack of adequate digital infrastructure for data storage and access Concerns about intellectual property and data misuse Limited collaboration among professionals in the field I have no difficulties in sharing data Other (please specify) _____
What are the main challenges in integrating digital technologies into your restoration or conservation workflow?	Lack of training or technical expertise High costs of digital tools or equipment Difficulty integrating digital data with traditional documentation or methods Limited institutional support or infrastructure Resistance to change from colleagues or stakeholders No significant difficulties Other (please specify): _____
Have you ever used 3D models in your work (e.g., for documentation, visualization, planning, research, or public engagement)?	Yes, frequently Yes, occasionally No, but I would be interested No, and I don't see the relevance for my work
Have you ever used digital simulations in your work (e.g., modelling degradation, testing restoration scenarios, simulating visitor flows or environmental impacts)?	Yes, frequently Yes, occasionally No, but I would be interested No, and I don't see the relevance for my work
In which areas do you think Digital Twins could be most useful in your field?	Collaboration between institutions to develop and share interoperable Digital Twin models Real-time monitoring of conservation conditions Simulation of environmental factors' impact on material degradation Virtual planning and testing of restoration interventions Creation of digital archives for restoration documentation Support for training and education in conservation I don't see relevant applications Other (please specify) _____
What kind of information or support would you expect from a Reactive Digital Twin to assist your conservation decisions?	Current condition of the object based on the latest data (e.g., imaging, sensors) Forecast of material deterioration due to environmental factors Simulations of potential restoration actions and their long-term effects Alerts and notifications in case of critical changes in the object's condition Access to historical conservation data and documentation Tools to compare before/after states or test scenarios Other (please specify): _____

<p>How do you see the evolution of Digital Twin usage in the conservation and restoration sector in the coming years?</p>	<p>They will become an essential tool for cultural heritage management They will be useful only in specific contexts They will remain marginal due to costs and technical complexities I don't believe they will have a significant impact in this field I'm not sure</p>
<p>Would you (or your institution, if applicable) be willing to share data to support collaborative research or the development of digital services within the ARTEMIS project?</p>	<p>Yes, without major restrictions Yes, under specific conditions (e.g., licensing, metadata only, anonymization) No, due to legal or institutional restrictions It depends on the type of data involved I'm not sure / It's not up to me Other (please specify): _____</p>
<p>Would you be interested in learning more about the possibility of proposing a pilot case study for the ARTEMIS project? (Pilots are real-world examples where ARTEMIS tools and services can be tested and demonstrated in collaboration with heritage professionals and institutions. Proposals are non-binding and will be evaluated later in the project based on feasibility and relevance. A pilot typically involves a cultural heritage asset, a clear objective, relevant data and technologies, and specific target users or stakeholders.</p>	

FINAL SECTION

<p>How familiar are you with the following digital skills and topics?</p>	<p>Digital Twins potentialities and advantages (e.g., real-time data, decision support)</p>
	<p>2D/3D digitisation (e.g. scanning, photogrammetry, GIS)</p>
	<p>Creating or editing 3D models (e.g. mesh editing, modelling software)</p>
	<p>Using or navigating 3D simulations (e.g., virtual walkthroughs, scenario exploration)</p>
	<p>Analysing data from 3D simulations (e.g., condition monitoring, material behaviour analysis)</p>
	<p>Using AR/VR tools in cultural heritage (e.g., virtual exhibitions, AR applications)</p>
	<p>IoT / loCT services (e.g., sensor networks, remote monitoring)</p>
	<p>Working with digital environments / virtual machines (e.g., cloud platforms, emulated lab setups)</p>
	<p>Metadata standards (e.g. Dublin Core, LIDO)</p>
	<p>Semantic data modelling (e.g. CIDOC CRM, ontologies)</p>
<p>Managing or aggregating data from different sources (e.g., database integration, harvesting protocols)</p>	
<p>Would you be interested in participating in one of the training activities organized by the ARTEMIS project?</p>	<p>Yes, I would like to receive more information and apply Maybe, it depends on the content and format No, I am not interested</p>

<p>Do you or your institution use or manage any digital tool, application, or system that might be of interest for ARTEMIS? (This could be something developed in-house, used in your daily work, or created in a past project. Feel free to mention it below if you wish — this is completely optional.)</p> <p>If you'd like, briefly describe the resource here: (What it does, who uses it, and anything else you'd like to share)</p>	
<p>Would you like to subscribe to the ARTEMIS project newsletter to stay informed about project developments?</p>	<p>Yes, I would like to subscribe No, thank you Maybe later</p>
<p>Please leave your contact details</p>	<p>Name: _____ Email: _____ Institution (optional) _____</p>
<p>Is there any other aspect you consider important to take into account? Feel free to share any opinions or thoughts.</p>	

TRAINING SECTION

<p>If a dedicated training for the use of digital services in your field were available, which format would you prefer?</p>	<p>Online training (webinars, e-learning courses) In-person workshops with practical sessions Hybrid training (part online, part in-person) Practical guides and downloadable manuals No preference</p>
<p>Are you familiar with one of these learning platforms?</p>	<p>Europeana Pro ARIADNEplus Training Hub Programming Historian DARIAH Campus CARARE OER Commons Other (please specify) _____</p>
<p>What is your main working language?</p>	<p>Please specify: _____</p>
<p>Would you be interested in learning more about these topics? (Please select all that apply)</p>	<p>Digital Twins potentialities and advantages (e.g., real-time data, decision support) 2D/3D digitisation (e.g., photogrammetry, laser scanning, GIS) Creating or editing 3D models (e.g., mesh editing, modelling software) Using or navigating 3D simulations (e.g., virtual walkthroughs, scenario exploration) Analysing data from 3D simulations (e.g., condition monitoring, material behaviour analysis) Using AR/VR tools in cultural heritage (e.g., virtual exhibitions, AR applications) IoT / loCT services (e.g., sensor networks, remote monitoring) Working with digital environments / virtual machines (e.g., cloud platforms, emulated lab setups) Metadata standards (e.g., Dublin Core, LIDO) Semantic data modelling (e.g., CIDOC CRM, ontologies) Managing or aggregating data from different sources (e.g., database integration, harvesting protocols)</p>
<p>How do you plan to apply the acquired skills in your work?</p>	<p>Improve research and analysis methodologies Integrate new technologies into my projects Train colleagues and students in my professional field Develop collaborations with other institutions Other (please specify) _____</p>
<p>Would you like to share anything else about your experience with online learning and your needs for training resources?</p>	